

A STUDY ON THE STATE OF FOOD PROCESSING UNITS IN CHITTOOR DISTRICT OF ANDHRA PRADESH

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ABSTRACT

The essential requirements for human sustenance are air, water and food. Man has travelled distance destination in search of food and fodder. Human existence and survival depend on food and in fact, all living creatures require food for its survival. For a country like India with more than a billion populations, this food processing opens enormous opportunities. India is experiencing a great momentum in embracing the organic revolution. Though the Indian Organic Food industry is at its slow pace, the growth is significant in past few years. The Food processing industry is growing with a rapid rate and has a great-untapped potential to lead the economy to progress (Khan F M and Ahmad S, 2014). Not only being just another form of industry, but for India's development, food processing industry is very essential as it help to bridge the gap between two pillars of economy, namely industry and agriculture (Salman H and Bhargava P.K, 2016). Chittoor district in Andhra Pradesh is recognized for the presence of several agro-based units. Particularly the importance of various food-processing units is considerable. To understand the state of food processing units in Chittoor district and profile of various entrepreneurs who are running these units, a study is carried out. Chittoor district is a center for food processing units due to the availability of raw material abundantly. This paved the path for the development of food processing units in this area. An attempt has been made in this paper to discuss about the prospects and problems of these food-processing units.

KEYWORDS

Food Processing, Entrepreneurs, Entrepreneurial Motivation, Problems etc.

INTRODUCTION

Food Processing units occupy a significant position in the rural economy of Andhra Pradesh. This state is an agrarian state and vast majority of the population directly depends on agriculture. For a developing economy, both agriculture and industry are two wheels. When these two wheels are properly propelled then only it is said to be the development. Due to its soil, water availability, vegetables, and fruits are abundantly cultivated in and around Chittoor district. Farmers are not getting remunerative price and at the same time, cost of cultivation is growing without leaps and bounds. Most of the cultivators are unable to understand the opportunities available to them and due to their low income and education unable to grab the avenues available to them. Middlemen have exploited this situation and neither the cultivator nor the customer is not benefitting. Only the middlemen are controlling the procurement costs and sometimes the farmers are not getting the input costs. Consequently, they are throwing their produce on the streets. Understanding this scenario some enthusiastic entrepreneurs has started their ventures in three forms such as individual units, small and medium units. Corporate units are also in vogue and slowly the entrepreneurial activity has been taken momentum.

Food processing industry is of great importance for India's development. They complement the agriculture production to reach the customers with varying needs. Food processing industries are very essential as they help bridge the gap between the two pillars of economy, namely industry and agriculture.

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Globally, India occupies 2nd position only next to China, in terms of overall food production. India's position is stable at the first slot in the global arena when it comes to production of milk. India also tops in producing fruits such as guavas, mangoes, papayas, and bananas. In producing other products like ginger, okra and buffalo meat also India occupies predominant position. In producing certain items such as green peas, potatoes, tea, tomato, and sesame, India stands at the 2nd position. Indian food processing sector is the first in terms of employment and tops in the number of factories being operated. Also, India ranks 3rd in terms of output.

India accounts to the production of nearly 450 million tons of raw food materials. These are from the plants and of animal origin. The raw forms of food are refined, stored and transformed into various usable products using conventional and modern postharvest and food processing technology. In food processing several activities are involved such as cleaning, grading, drying, storage, milling, packaging, transport, marketing and utilization.

In India, the post-harvest losses amount to nearly Rs. 76,000 Crores per annum, this is an indication of the bad stage through which the industry is passing. The basic purpose of food processing is aimed at preparing the food ready for consumption. Technically, any act involving conversion of raw ingredients into another consumable form is known as food processing. The simple process is that various vegetables and fruits will be converted for ready to use or eat. The food processing units does not require laborious manufacturing process. Simple processing is enough and the customer expects good storage life.

Highly processed foods are made from combinations of unprocessed food, minimally processed food and processed food ingredients. In recent times, health consciousness among the people has been growing and they are of the view that indiscriminate usage of pesticides is the cause of cancer and other dreaded diseases. Hence, they are giving utmost importance to organic fruits and vegetables or to the organic foods such Chips, Marmalades, Zellys, pickles and jams.

India is experiencing a great momentum in encouraging the organic revolution. Even though it is at its lowest ebb and slowing being ground gradually. The food processing basket consists of several varieties and forms It covers fruits and vegetables, dairy, edible oils, meat and poultry, non-alcoholic beverages, grain-based products, marine products, sugar and sugar-based products, alcoholic beverages, pulses, aerated beverages, malted beverages, spices, and salt. Out of these segments, dairy (16%), grain-based Products (34%), bakery-based products (20%), and fish and meat products (14%) contribute to a major portion of industry revenues, apart from the manufacture of beverages.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Sriraman Parthasarathy, (2008) in his article "Indian Food Processing Industry – A Snapshot" stated that the India contributes to less than 1.5% of international food trade, indicating the scope of gains for the exporters as well as investors to tap fully from the Indian food processing industry.

FICCI (2010) in its report on "Bottlenecks in Indian Food Processing Industry" concluded that The Indian food industry presents a very huge opportunity to every stakeholder. FICCI survey initiated the first efforts in identifying the challenges. This also helped create a guideline framework to the interested parties and stakeholders to harness the potential of food processing industry.

Sitalakshmi. S (2010) in her article, "Towards Achieving a Second Green Revolution – The Role of radiation technology in food processing management" stated that there is an urgent need for developing economies like India to utilize the technological advances made by BRIT to revamp the food processing sector. Starting from deregulation of the sector to investing in Research and Development facilities, to providing post-harvest storage facilities and marketing infrastructure, to linking economic policies to investments in agricultural extension services, a lot of ground has been cleared for the successful implementation of radiation technology.

Sreenivasa Murthy.K and Himachalam Dasaraju (2011) in their article "Problems of Fruit Processing Industry in Andhra Pradesh - A Case Study of Select Units in Chittoor" attempted to review the status of fruit processing industry and the problems encountered by the industry in Chittoor District of Andhra Pradesh. The Chittoor Fruit Processing Cluster (CFPC) is among the largest cluster of its kind in India. Factors such as lack of mutual trust,

intense inter-firm competition and a roller-coaster performance helped the cluster grow prior to the interventions in 1998.

Surendra P. Singh et al (2012) in their article “The Food Processing Industry in India: Challenges and Opportunities” revealed that while on one hand India’s agricultural base is quite strong but very low processing of food products and very high amounts of wastage are witnessed.

Kakali Majumdar (2013) in his article “Export Performance of Processed Food in India” stated that the Indian food processing industry is primarily export oriented. With the export growth rate of around 15%, its share in the international market is only 1.7%. Again, only 2% of the total food produced in India is processed for further consumption. This is a matter of concern that despite massive potential, this sector remains grossly underutilized.

Khan F M and Ahmad S (2014) in their article “Managerial issues for Green Marketing in Food Processing Industry of India” stated that the food processing industry is fast growing and has a tremendous potential to support the country’s economy. Food processing units can also make use of the green marketing concept both in its domestic and global operations. Products, processes, packaging, delivery, and advertising areas of food processing can be brought under green marketing.

Sridhar Murthy T.M. and Yogesh M, S. (2014) in their article “An overview of Food Processing Industry in India- Challenges and Opportunities” opined positively about the vast opportunities Indian food industry offers to all the stakeholders. Consumer demand is the prime driver for the industry while other drivers include the changing nature of the Indian consumer, who is more informed and willing to try new products and the strong production base of the country.

Rajender Kumar et al (2016) in their article “Agro Processing Industries in Haryana: Status, Problems and Prospects” stated that the agro processing assumed vital importance particularly in a state like Haryana where agriculture production has reached on plateau. Its importance became more elevated when employment opportunities in rural areas are squeezed. This paper analyzed the growth of village level agro industries for different periods and prioritized the factors hindering agro industrialization in Haryana. It is evident from the results traditional processing of village oil ghani, and jaggery and khandsari not keeping pace with time whereas cereal and pulses processing industries and fruits preservation and processing gaining movement in recent period.

Salman Hyder and P.K.Bhargava (2016) in their article “Indian food processing industry - opportunities and challenges” stated that the significance of food processing industry is very high. Not only being just another form of industry, but for India's development, food processing industries are very essential as they help bridge the gap between two pillars of economy, namely industry and agriculture.

Rewa Singh and Ravindra Tripathi (2017) in their article “Food Processing Industries: An Engine for Growth in Uttar Pradesh” India is an agrarian economy where more than 70% of the population largely depends on agricultural and allied activities for its livelihood. Despite this, Indian farmers are in very poor socioeconomic condition. They are in low-income equilibrium trap.

Sannamelam Murali Mohan and Jayachandra K, (2018) in their article “Marketing Problems of Agro Based Industries in Andhra Pradesh: With Special Reference to Chittoor District” revealed that the agro based industries are seen as part of the sunrise sector of the Indian economy. They offer vast potential for growth. Besides, they also create employment thus ensuring socio-economic impact through income generation.

Chittoor district is recognized for the presence of several agro-based industries. Particularly the importance of various food-processing industries is considerable. They are playing significant role in contributing to the food processing business to the state as well as meeting the export requirements. In this context, a study on food processing industries in Chittoor district is taken up.

METHODOLOGY

The present study is aimed to understand the state of food processing units in Chittoor district. To understand the profile of various entrepreneurs who are running these units and the problems and prospects of these food-processing units, a well-structured questionnaire was developed. The questionnaire was administered to the entrepreneurs in this region who own different forms of food processing units. The questionnaire was revised after consultation with experts and after a simple pilot survey. Using simple random sampling method, the sample was chosen. The sample size is 230.

To get better understanding and interpret the results of the present study, secondary data from the records, articles and other documentary materials was collected from industry reports, newspapers, magazines, etc. and are included in the study.

Objectives of the study

The objectives of the study are:

- To study the profile of entrepreneurs of food processing units.
- To examine the factors of motivation in promotion of food processing units.
- To analyze the problems faced by the food processing units.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Gender wise Distribution of Entrepreneurs

Table-1

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Female	6	2.6	2.6	2.6
Male	224	97.4	97.4	100.0
Total	230	100.0	100.0	

Sources: Authors Compilation

The gender wise distribution of respondents is presented in table-1. The data shows that most of the entrepreneurs running food-processing units are male. Of the total respondents, 97.4 percent are male, while only 2.6 percent are female.

Educational Qualification of Entrepreneurs

Table-2

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
General	83	36.1	36.1	36.1
Technical	147	63.9	63.9	100.0
Total	230	100.0	100.0	

Sources: Authors Compilation

The distribution of respondents as per their educational qualification is presented in table-2. The data indicates that a majority of the entrepreneurs in food processing units are from a technical background amounting to 63.9 percent of the total respondents. The respondents with other general educational background were representing 36.1 percent of the total respondents.

Distribution of Respondents Based on Segment of Unit

Table-3

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Bread & Bakery	23	10.0	10.0	10.0
Cereals Processing	6	2.6	2.6	12.6
Confectionary Consumer Products	23	10.0	10.0	22.6
Edible Oils	6	2.6	2.6	25.2
Fruits and Vegetable	37	16.1	16.1	41.3
Grain Processing	23	10.0	10.0	51.3
Meat, Poultry And Fishery	12	5.2	5.2	56.5
Milk And Milk Products	23	10.0	10.0	66.5
Mineral Water	17	7.4	7.4	73.9
Papad, Pickles, Chutany	11	4.8	4.8	78.7
Soft Drinks	35	15.2	15.2	93.9
Spices	14	6.1	6.1	100.0
Total	230	100.0	100.0	

Sources: Authors Compilation

Business Practice Experience of Entrepreneurs in Food Processing Units

Table-4

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
2 to 4 years	82	35.7	35.7	35.7
4 to 6 years	28	12.2	12.2	47.8
6 to 8 years	15	6.5	6.5	54.3
8 years	11	4.8	4.8	59.1
Up to 2 years	94	40.9	40.9	100
Total	230	100	100	

Sources: Authors Compilation

The data in table-4 presents that 40.9 percent of the respondents are having units with less than 2 years of business practice experience. 35.7 percent of respondents are having units with 2 to 4 years of business practice experience. While 4.8 percent of the respondents are having units with 8 years or above years of business practice experience others are in between the ranges.

Location of Food Processing Units

Table-5

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Rural	80	34.8	34.8	34.8
Semi-urban	62	27.0	27.0	61.7
Urban	88	38.3	38.3	100.0
Total	230	100.0	100.0	

Sources: Authors Compilation

The data in table-5 indicates that 34.8 percent of units are present in rural areas and 27 percent of the units are located in semi-urban areas. The remaining 38.3 percent of units are located in urban areas.

Motivational Factors for Starting of Food Processing Unit

Table-6

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Cooperative Society Managements	33	14.3	14.3	14.3
Family Business	64	27.8	27.8	42.2
Government Programmes	28	12.2	12.2	54.3
Self Help Groups	26	11.3	11.3	65.7
Self-motivation	79	34.3	34.3	100.0
Total	230	100.0	100.0	

Sources: Authors Compilation

The motivational factors that led to the starting of food processing units by the respondents are presented in Table 6. The data shows that 14.3 percent of the respondents cited cooperative society managements as the factor, while 27.8 percent of the respondents cited family business as the factor. It is observed that self-motivation is the factor that highest percent of respondents cited as motivation, representing 34.3 percent of the total respondents. On the other hand, 12.2 percent quoted government programmes and 11.3 percent quoted self-help groups as the factor of motivation for starting food-processing unit.

Mode through Which the Unit is Promoted

Table-7

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Not Under Any Government Programme	119	51.7	51.7	51.7
P.M.R.Y.	58	25.2	25.2	77.0
S.H.G.	12	5.2	5.2	82.2
Swarnjayanti Gram Swarozgar Yojana	41	17.8	17.8	100.0
Total	230	100.0	100.0	

Sources: Authors Compilation

The government programme under which the respondents are operating business is presented in table 7. The data shows that 51.7 percent of the respondents' businesses are not under any government programme. 25.2 percent have indicated to be under the PMRY, 17.8 percent are under Swarnjayanti Gram Swarozgar Yojana, and 5.2 percent are under SHG.

Source of Business Finance

Table-8

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Bank, Financial Institutions	96	41.7	41.7	41.7
Own Friends, Relatives	75	32.6	32.6	74.3
Private Finance.	49	21.3	21.3	95.7
Self Help Group	10	4.3	4.3	100.0
Total	230	100.0	100.0	

Sources: Authors Compilation

The source of business finance for the enterprises is presented in table 8. A majority of 41.7 percent of the enterprises received finance from banks and financial institutions. 32.6 percent of the enterprises have relied on own friends and relatives for the finance. 21.3 percent of the enterprises reported to have taken private finance. Another 4.3 percent of the enterprises have received finance from Self Help Groups.

Completion of Training / Special Course for Food Processing Unit

Table-9

	N	Percent	Percent of Cases
Conferences Seminar Attended	47	14.8	20.43
Dic Training Completed	35	10.9	15.22
Food Processing Diploma Completed	148	46.1	64.35
No Training Obtained	91	28.3	39.57
Total	321	100	139.57

Sources: Authors Compilation

The data on whether any training/special course for food processing unit was completed is presented in table 9. The data reveals that 14.8 percent of respondents attended conferences/seminars, 10.9 percent respondents completed DIC training, 46.1 percent respondents completed diploma in food processing, whereas remaining 28.3 percent of respondents did not obtain any training.

Help from the Government Agencies in Obtaining Raw Materials

Table-10

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
May be	58	25.2	25.2	25.2
No	75	32.6	32.6	57.8
Yes	97	42.2	42.2	100.0
Total	230	100.0	100.0	

Sources: Authors Compilation

Data pertaining to whether any help is received from the government agencies in obtaining the raw materials is presented in table-10. The data shows that 32.6 percent of the respondents did not receive any help from government agencies in obtaining raw materials. 42.2 percent of the respondents received help from government agencies in obtaining raw materials. Whereas 25.2 percent of respondents could not say exactly whether they received help from government agencies in obtaining raw materials.

Technology Being Used in the Business Unit

Table 11

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Manual	48	20.9	20.9	20.9
Modern Technology & Machinery	89	38.7	38.7	59.6
Old Machinery and Techniques	28	12.2	12.2	71.7
Only Grading, Packaging and Distribution	20	8.7	8.7	80.4
Partially Using of Machinery	45	19.6	19.6	100.0
Total	230	100.0	100.0	

Sources: Authors Compilation

The technology being used in the business units under study is presented in table 11. The data shows that 20.9 percent of units under study are using manual methods. 38.7 percent of units are using modern technology and machinery. 12.2 percent of units are using old machinery and techniques. 8.7 percent of units are using technology for only grading, packaging, and distribution. 19.6 percent of units are using machinery partially only.

Marketing Problems Faced by the Food Processing Units

Table-12

	N	Percent	Percent of Cases
Channels	35	9.1	15.22
Competition	132	34.3	57.39
Improper Distribution	61	15.7	26.52
Inadequate Transport Facilities	62	16.1	26.96
Ineffective Salesmen	14	3.5	6.09
Lack of Storage Facilities	82	21.3	35.65
Total	386	100	167.83

Sources: Authors Compilation

The data about usual market problems faced by the unit is presented in table 12. The data shows that 9.1 percent of the units under study are facing channels related marketing problems. 34.3 percent of units are facing competition as a problem for marketing. 15.7 percent of units are facing marketing problems due to improper distribution. 16.1 percent of units are facing marketing problems due to inadequate transport facilities. 3.5 percent of the units are facing problems due to ineffective salesmen. Whereas, 21.3 percent of the units are facing marketing problems due to lack of storage facilities.

Food Safety Measures Adopted in Food Processing

Table-13

	N	Percent	Percent of Cases
Checking by Food Inspectors	55	17	23.91
Continuous Testing of Products at Laboratory	79	24.3	34.35
Internal Control	7	2.2	3.04
Obtained and Followed Standard Grade	23	7	10.00
Quality Manufacturing or Processing Practices	118	36.5	51.30
Strictly Followed Government Regulations	42	13	18.26
Total	324	100	140.87

Sources: Authors Compilation

The food safety measures adopted by the units under study for food processing are presented in table 13. Of the total units under study, 17 percent of the units are going through checking by food inspectors. 24.3 percent are using continuous testing of products at laboratory. While 2.2 percent units are using internal control, 7 percent have obtained and followed standard grade. 36.5 percent of units are using quality manufacturing or processing practices, whereas remaining 13 percent are strictly following government regulations.

Problems identified

- Marketing problems are more.
- Transportation is a problem.
- Availability of skilled manpower is low.
- Power problems are persistent.
- Government support is minimal.

CONCLUSION

The data analysis of the present study indicated that most of the entrepreneurs running food processing industries are male (97.4 percent). The entrepreneurs in food processing industries are from a technical background (63.9 percent).

40.9 percent of the entrepreneurs are having units with less than 2 years of business practice experience while 35.7 percent are having units with 2 to 4 years of business practice experience. While 27.8 percent of the entrepreneurs are motivated due to family business, 34.3 percent due to self-motivation and 12.2 percent due to government programmes. 46.1 percent of entrepreneurs completed diploma in food processing. 34.3 percent of units are facing competition as a problem for marketing. 21.3 percent of the units are facing marketing problems due to lack of storage facilities. 15.7 percent of units are facing marketing problems due to improper distribution whereas 16.1 percent of units are facing marketing problems due to inadequate transport facilities.

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